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Crop-Specific Effects of Data Augmentation on Classification Accuracy in Sentinel-2 Imagery

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of data augmentation techniques on crop classification using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery. The DACIA5 dataset (2020-2024) comprising 12 crop classes and high-quality in situ labels was used to train a ResNet18 model adapted for 12-channel multispectral input to perform crop classification. An imbalanced data sampling strategy was employed to address class disparities, and various augmentation techniques were tested to assess their impact on model performance. The outcomes of this research show that the augmentation effects vary significantly by crop type, with some techniques improving classification for certain crops while degrading performance for others. These findings contribute to our understanding of the challenges associated with crop-specific classification in remote sensing applications and underscore the need for tailored augmentation approaches.

Keywords: *Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, crop identification, data augmentation, class imbalance*

1 Introduction

Accurate crop identification and monitoring are essential for the success of modern agriculture, and require advanced classification models capable of interpreting complex multispectral imagery. Machine learning techniques based on patterns extracted from large-scale data offer promising solutions to this task. However, despite significant advances in remote sensing technologies, crop identification remains constrained by fundamental limitations: the scarcity of comprehensive, accurately labeled datasets, and the diverse and evolving nature of farmland conditions. Many existing datasets suffer from inaccurate ground truth annotations, limited temporal coverage, or inadequate representation of crop diversity, ultimately limiting the ability of these models to generalize effectively [1] - [5].

This study explores the challenge of crop identification using the multispectral dataset DACIA5 [6], which was carefully assembled from Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. The data set covers a 5-year period (2020-2024) in the Braşov region of Romania and includes 12 distinct crop types with carefully validated in situ labels. To properly evaluate the generalization capabilities of the model, we implemented a temporal data split strategy, using images from 2020-2023 for training purposes while reserving data from 2024 for independent testing. This temporal separation allowed for a thorough assessment of the model's performance on newly acquired imagery.

A significant challenge in machine learning-based crop classification is the presence of class imbalance, where certain crop types are disproportionately represented while others are underrepresented. This imbalance has the potential to introduce bias, thereby affecting the model's capacity

to accurately identify the less prevalent crop categories. To address this issue, we systematically explore data augmentation techniques as a potential strategy to improve model robustness and representational capacity.

The present study investigates how various data augmentation strategies affect ResNet18 convolutional neural network performance in crop identification. By implementing specific geometric and spectral transformations, we examine whether targeted augmentation techniques can reduce model bias and enhance classification accuracy.

Our analysis evaluates diverse augmentation approaches and their impact on classification performance across different crop types. Results indicate that while certain augmentations improve generalization to the 2024 test set, their effectiveness varies considerably, with limited improvements for underrepresented classes.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the DACIA5 dataset, the experimental setup, the deep learning model architecture, and the augmentation strategies. Section 3 presents the results of the crop identification study, along with comparative analyses. Finally, the concluding section 4 synthesizes the findings and explores directions for future research.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Dataset

This study uses DACIA5, a geospatial dataset derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite images that covers agricultural fields in the Brasov region of Romania over a five-year period (2020-2024). Although DACIA5 encompasses both radar and optical data, the present study focuses exclusively on its multispectral component for crop identification.

The dataset is unique in its crop-specific labeling, temporal coverage, and geospatial accuracy. Each image corresponds to one of twelve distinct crop classes, including common winter wheat, corn, corn silage, peas, winter rapeseed, late potatoes, some other potato crops, common spring wheat, soybean, sugar beets, alfalfa and alfalfa special. The temporal span of DACIA5 encompasses multiple growing seasons, thereby enabling analysis of inter-annual crop phenology patterns and environmental variability. The dataset is sourced from parcels cultivated by the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet in Brasov, ensuring precise ground truth labels through extensive in-situ field observations. Each sample in the dataset consists of a $32 \times 32 \times 12$ multispectral patch capturing all Sentinel-2 spectral bands. Patches were selected to ensure that at least 75% of the area was covered by a single crop type. We applied a temporal train-test split: 5436 patches from 2020 to 2023 were used for training, and 1017 patches from 2024 served as a test set. Due to crop rotation practices, only 8 of the 12 classes in the training set appear in the test set, creating an additional generalization challenge. As illustrated in Table 1, the distribution of patches across crop types reveals a substantial class imbalance.

2.2 Model Architecture and Training Procedure

To identify crop types, a pretrained ResNet18 model from the PyTorch library was chosen. This model was selected for its effectiveness in processing small image patches while maintaining computational feasibility. Given the multispectral nature of Sentinel-2 imagery, the network architecture was modified to accept 12-channel input data instead of the standard 3-channel RGB input. This modification was implemented by substituting the initial convolutional layer with a newly designed Conv2D layer, which was engineered to process 12 input channels. The final fully connected layer

Table 1: Distribution of patches in training and test sets

Crop Type	Train	Test
Common winter wheat	750	132
Corn	1577	75
Corn silage	1001	0
Peas	116	48
Winter rapeseed	200	303
Late potatoes	18	52
Other potato crop	13	0
Common spring wheat	212	16
Soybean	242	0
Sugar beets	906	320
Alfalfa special	241	0
Alfalfa	160	71
Total	5436	1017

was also modified to output 12 class probabilities, corresponding to the distinct crop types in the DACIA5 dataset.

2.2.1 Optimization and Loss Function

The network was optimized using AdamW [7], a variant of Adam that incorporates decoupled weight decay regularization. The selection of this optimizer was motivated by its improved handling of weight decay, which leads to better generalization. The cross-entropy loss function was employed as the objective function. All experiments were conducted in Google Colab’s T4 GPU environment, using PyTorch for model implementation and training.

2.2.2 Training Setup and Class Imbalance Handling

The training process was executed with a batch size of 128 patches. Due to the significant class imbalance observed in the dataset - as shown in Table 1 -, the Imbalanced Dataset Sampler from PyTorch was employed. This sampling strategy increased the frequency of underrepresented classes during training, improving feature learning without artificially duplicating samples or introducing excessive augmentation. This approach aligns with best practices for handling imbalanced datasets in deep learning, as discussed by [8].

2.2.3 Experimental Validation

In order to enhance statistical reliability while maintaining computational feasibility, each experimental configuration was trained multiple times. This approach accounts for variability introduced by stochastic optimization and parameter initialization. The evaluation of model performance was conducted through comprehensive analysis of confusion matrices across runs, allowing us to assess the accuracy variability for each crop type under different augmentation strategies. For each augmentation technique, we calculated the difference in classification accuracy compared to the no-augmentation baseline, providing direct measurement of each transformation’s impact on model performance. This differential analysis enabled us to identify crop-specific patterns in augmentation response and quantify both beneficial and detrimental effects.

2.3 Data Augmentation Strategies

The augmentation strategy employed in this study comprises three categories of transformations, which address different aspects of satellite imagery variability.

2.3.1 Spectral and Spatial Variability Augmentations

Satellite imagery exhibits inherent variations in spectral reflectance due to environmental conditions and acquisition artifacts. To simulate these variations, we implemented random region swapping, which exchanges rectangular regions within patches to simulate field heterogeneity caused by variations in planting density and soil moisture. We also applied random pixel dropout, which selectively removes pixel values to simulate missing data from sensor noise or atmospheric interference. Additionally, random rectangle erasure removes contiguous regions to simulate cloud masking and environmental obstructions, encouraging the model to rely on broader contextual information rather than potentially unreliable localized features.

2.3.2 Geometric Augmentations

While agricultural parcels maintain consistent physical orientation, satellite imagery captures them from various perspectives and orbital paths. To address positional biases, we implemented horizontal and vertical flipping to prevent orientation-specific biases, exposing the model to mirrored versions of the data to improve generalization across diverse field arrangements. Additionally, rotational augmentation systematically rotated patches with random angles to prevent overfitting to specific spatial alignments corresponding to particular satellite trajectories, ensuring robust feature representations across varying imaging geometries.

2.3.3 Combined Augmentation Strategy

In addition to evaluating each transformation independently, we tested a comprehensive combined strategy that integrated all techniques into a single training pipeline.

Each augmentation approach was evaluated under identical training conditions and systematically compared against a non-augmented baseline to assess its impact on classification performance.

3 Crop Identification Results

The evaluation of crop identification performance revealed significant variations in classification accuracy across different crop types. The mean confusion matrix shown in Figure 1 illustrates these variations without augmentation, serving as our baseline for assessing the effectiveness of subsequent transformations.

Without augmentation, the model demonstrated varying levels of performance. Sugar beets (75.39%) and peas (73.44%) exhibited the highest classification accuracy, followed by alfalfa (65.14%), winter wheat (62.88%), and corn (61.33%). Notably, peas performed exceptionally well despite having relatively limited training data (116 training patches), contradicting the expectation that data scarcity would necessarily lead to poorer performance. Winter rapeseed exhibited limited classification accuracy (32.51%), while late potatoes demonstrated poor performance (15.87%), aligning with expectations given their extremely limited training samples (only 18 training patches). Several crop types present in the training set, including corn silage, soybean, other potato, and alfalfa special, were not represented in the 2024 test set due to crop rotation practices, and thus couldn't be evaluated for classification performance.

Figure 1: Mean confusion matrix without augmentation

The analysis of classification patterns reveals substantial confusion between certain crop types. Late potatoes were frequently misclassified as sugar beet (34.62%) or corn (18.75%), suggesting spectral similarities between these crops. Winter rapeseed showed significant confusion with winter wheat (23.84%) and sugar beet (16.91%), while maintaining only 32.51% correct classification. Spring wheat was predominantly misclassified as winter wheat (40.62%) or corn silage (28.12%). These misclassification patterns highlight the challenges in distinguishing spectrally similar crops, especially with limited training examples.

3.1 Impact of Data Augmentation on Classification Performance

The differential analysis of augmentation effects on crop classification accuracy revealed distinct patterns across crop types and transformation techniques. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate these differences through boxplots comparing each augmentation strategy to the no-augmentation baseline, while Figures 2 and 3 show the absolute accuracy variability across different augmentation methods.

3.2 Crop-Specific Augmentation Responses

Our analysis revealed clear crop-specific patterns in response to various augmentation techniques:

- **Peas** consistently demonstrated positive responses to most augmentations, with accuracy improvements of 10–25% across geometric transformations (Figure 4(d), Figure 5(e), and Figure 5(f)). This suggests that peas possess distinctive spectral signatures that remain identifiable even under substantial transformation, as also evident in their high baseline accuracy (Figure 2(a)).
- **Winter rapeseed** showed substantial benefits from Rotation (up to +40% in some cases, Figure 5(f)) and All Transforms (+10–20%, Figure 5(g)), indicating that orientation variability enhances its classification accuracy.

- **Corn** exhibited the highest variability in response, benefiting modestly from Random Rectangle Erasure (+5–10%, Figure 4(c)) but suffering significant accuracy degradation with Random Pixel Dropout (-30%, Figure 4(b)). This suggests that while corn can tolerate some spatial modifications, pixel-level information remains essential for its identification.
- **Sugar beet** and **alfalfa** responded negatively to most augmentations, with Horizontal Flip causing particularly severe degradation (-20 to -40% for sugar beet and -45 to -50% for alfalfa, Figure 4(d)), indicating that both crops have orientation-specific features essential for correct identification.
- **Late potato** maintained consistently poor performance regardless of augmentation strategy, as visible across all plots in Figures 2 and 3, suggesting that its classification challenges stem from factors beyond what augmentation can address.

Figure 2: Accuracy Variability by Augmentation (Part 1)

(a) Horizontal Flip

(b) Vertical Flip

(c) Rotation

(d) All Transforms

Figure 3: Accuracy Variability by Augmentation (Part 2)

(a) Random Region Swap vs. the baseline

(b) Random Pixel Dropout vs. the baseline

(c) Random Rectangle Erasure vs. the baseline

(d) Horizontal Flip vs. the baseline

Figure 4: Accuracy Differences (Part 1)

Figure 5: Accuracy Differences (Part 2)

3.3 Technique-Specific Effectiveness

Analysis of individual augmentation techniques revealed varying degrees of utility:

- **Rotation** (Figure 5(f) and Figure 3(g)) demonstrated pronounced effectiveness for certain crops (peas, winter rapeseed) while significantly degrading performance for others (sugar beet, -35%), highlighting the importance of orientation in crop identification.
- **Random Rectangle Erasure** (Figure 4(c) and Figure 2(d)) emerged as the most balanced augmentation strategy, providing modest benefits for several crops (corn, winter wheat) with minimal negative impact on others. This suggests that simulating partial occlusions may improve model generalization by encouraging reliance on broader contextual features.
- **Horizontal Flip and Vertical Flip** (Figure 4(d), Figure 5(e), and Figure 3(e) and 3(f)) showed highly selective benefits, primarily for peas, while causing substantial accuracy degradation for sugar beet and alfalfa. This confirms that directional transformations can disrupt essential classification features for certain crops.
- **Random Pixel Dropout** (Figure 4(b) and Figure 2(c)) generally reduced accuracy across most crops, with corn experiencing the largest decline (-30%), indicating that preserving pixel-level information is important for accurate classification.
- **Combined application** of all transformations (Figure 5(g), Figure 3(h)) demonstrated mixed results, providing substantial benefits for winter wheat, peas, and winter rapeseed while significantly degrading performance for corn, sugar beet, and alfalfa.

3.4 Practical Implications

These findings show that augmentation effectiveness in crop classification is highly crop-dependent, contradicting the common assumption that data augmentation universally improves model performance. Based on these results, we propose the following crop-specific augmentation re-recommendations:

- For crops with symmetric structures (e.g., peas): apply geometric transformations including Rotation (Figure 5(f)), Vertical Flip (Figure 5(e)), and Horizontal Flip (Figure 4(d)).
- For crops with variable responses (e.g., corn): use Random Rectangle Erasure (Figure 4(c)) selectively while avoiding Random Pixel Dropout (Figure 4(b)).
- For crops with strong directional features (e.g., winter rapeseed): apply Rotation-based augmentation (Figure 5(f)).
- For crops that perform poorly with augmentation (e.g., sugar beet, alfalfa): minimize transformations to preserve their distinguishing features, as evidenced by the negative impacts shown across most difference plots.
- For crops with consistently poor classification (e.g., late potato): consider alternative approaches such as enhanced feature engineering or targeted data collection rather than augmentation.

This tailored approach to augmentation respects the unique spectral and spatial characteristics of different crop types, potentially improving overall classification performance while avoiding detrimental transformations for sensitive crops.

4 Conclusions

This study explored data augmentation effects on crop identification using Sentinel-2 imagery. While some augmentation techniques helped model generalization, overall classification performance remained challenging, with certain techniques actually reducing accuracy for specific crops. The persistent difficulty with underrepresented crops suggests ResNet18, despite its effectiveness in other tasks, may not be optimal for handling the strong class imbalance in this dataset.

Our analysis revealed crop-specific augmentation responses. Peas benefited from geometric transformations, while sugar beet and alfalfa showed significant performance degradation with these same transformations, challenging the assumption of universal augmentation benefits. This highlights the need for crop-specific augmentation strategies in agricultural remote sensing.

Future work should explore alternative architectures better suited for imbalanced multispectral data, such as transformers or specialized models for remote sensing. Advanced augmentation techniques, including domain-specific synthetic data generation, could further enhance model robustness. Addressing these challenges is essential for improving crop classification accuracy in precision agriculture.

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